
Novel Synthesis and Properties of Tropically Derived Oils

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ABSTRACT

The physico-chemical characterization of *Prunus amygdalus*, *Dacryodes edulis* and *Chrysophyllum albidium* seed oils were investigated, together with their methyl esters. The vegetable oils were extracted by applying the solvent extraction method, using n-hexane. *Prunus amygdalus* had the highest oil yield (60.1%), followed by *Dyacrodes edulis* (55.76 %) and least from *Chrysophyllum albidium* (13.67%). The oils and their biodiesel were then analyzed for acid value, free fatty acid, specific gravity, ash content, iodine value, peroxide value, saponification value, kinematic viscosity, flash point, smoke point, titre value, cloud point, moisture content and refractive index. Accordingly, *Dyacrodes edulis* seed oil had the highest acid value of 6.57 and required two-step transesterification. The produced biodiesels were discussed in the light of ASTM D 9751, ASTM D 6751 and DIN 14214. These showed yields of 94.36%, 93.03% and 86.49%, cetane numbers of 70.40, 55.20 and 64.57 and calorific values of 31,178.39 KJ/kg, 34,421.50 KJ/kg and 32,838.38 KJ/kg for *Prunus amygdalus*, *Dacryodes edulis* and *Chrysophyllum albidium*, respectively. Other fuel-related properties showed highly improved qualities upon transesterification and compared well with ASTM and EU standards. The overall results showed that the seed oils are viable for biodiesel production.

Keywords: Vegetable oils, Physico-chemical Parameters, Transesterification; Biodiesel, Extraction

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1. INTRODUCTION

Direct use of vegetable oil as fuel for diesel engine has been observed to cause particle agglomeration and injector fouling due to its high viscosity and low volatility that is about 10 to 20 times greater than the values obtained from petroleum diesel. There are four techniques applied to reduce the high viscosity of vegetable oils and they are: dilution with pure ethanol or diesel fuel, micro emulsion with immiscible liquids, pyrolysis or thermal degradation of vegetable oils and transesterification. Among all these methods, transesterification seems to be the best option since the process can significantly reduce the high viscosity of vegetable oils (Fan, 2008). Furthermore, the physical properties of biodiesel produced by this simple process are very close to the petroleum diesel fuel. Transesterification is the displacement of alcohol from ester by another alcohol in process similar to hydrolysis except that alcohol is employed

instead of water (Srivatava and Prasad 2000). The transesterification process consists of a sequence of three consecutive reversible reactions which include conversion of triglycerides to monoglycerides. The glycerides are converted to glycerol and yield one ester molecule in each step. Since this reaction is reversible, excess amount of alcohol is often used to help drive the equilibrium towards the right. In the presence of excess alcohol, the forward reaction is pseudo-first order reaction and the reverse reaction is a second order reaction. Equation 1-3 consists of the sequential process while Equation 4 is the summary of the processes.

Triglycerides in oil **Alcohol** **Glycerol** **Fatty acid alkyl ester ester (FAAE)**

The choice of the catalyst and the nature of alcohol determine the type of initial species and the nature of Fatty Acid Alkyl Ester (FAAE) to be formed. Equation 5-9 shows the conventional mechanism of transesterification reaction process.

Mechanisms of the Transesterification Reaction Mechanism of the transesterification reaction with an alkaline catalyst

or

Step 1

Step 2

Step 3

where: R-OH – triglycerides, R₁ – long alkyl group and R' – short alkyl group.

The transesterification process involves the use of vegetable oil; hence, efforts are geared towards harnessing vegetable oil sources from several tropical plants to promote the application of renewable energy policies in the world oils but oils that are not staple foods are preferable to prevent food-fuel crises.

Almond plants are included in the family *Rosaceae* in addition to *prunoideae* (apples, pears), *prunoideae* (apricot, cherry, peach and plum) and *rosoideae* (blackberry, strawberry) fruits (Giwa and Ogunbona, 2014). There are two major varieties of almonds, the bitter almond (*Prunus amygdalus* “amara”) and the sweet almond (*Prunus amygdalus* “dulcis”) used mainly for culinary purposes and making of oils and flavourings respectively (Agunbiade and Olanlolukun, 2006). Sweet Almond (SA) fruit consists of three or correctly four portions of kernel or meat, middle shell, outer green shell cover or almond hull and a thin leathery layer known as brown meat or seed coat (Ali *et al.*, 2010).

Giwa and Ogunbona, 2014, has reported that *Prunus amygdalus dulcis* seed contains 51.45% oil, and yielded 85.90% biodiesel with oleic acid of 69.7%, linoleic acid of 18.2% and palmitic acid of 9.3% as predominant fatty acids. They reported that the fuel characteristics (cloud point; -3 °C and pour point; 9 °C) were within the limit of EN14214 and ASTM D6751 biodiesel standards. Sweet almond tree is predominant in the south eastern and south southern parts of Nigeria where they are basically grown for ornamental purposes. In these areas, the

fruits litter the environment and are either picked up by children or disposed of as wastes and as such their use as feedstock for biodiesel production would also serve as a waste disposal option in these areas.

African Star Apple (ASA) is one of the indigenous wild fruit trees with enormous potentials for establishment (Ureigho and Ekeke, 2010). It belongs to the family of sapotacea and naturally occurs in Nigeria, Uganda, Niger Republic, Cameroon and Cote d'ivoire (Adewusi and Bada, 1997). In Nigeria it is referred to as *Udara* in Igbo and *Agbalumo* in Yoruba. It grows as a wild plant which has up to 800 species and make up almost half of the order Ebernales and has become a crop of commercial value in recent times (Oboh *et al.*, 2009; Ehiagbonare *et al.*, 2008). It is an evergreen tree that grows up to 40m high and about 2m in girth with a straight-long fluted bole with small buttress of the base (Jayeoba *et al.*, 2007). It is found mainly in the rural and urban centres in the month of December to April (Audu *et al.*, 2013).

The fruit when ripe is ovoid to sub-globose, pointed at the apex up to 6cm long and 5cm in diameter with an orange to golden yellow skin or peel. Within the pulp are three to five seeds which are not usually eaten. The seeds are dark brown shiny, obliquely oloipsoid to ovoid up to 2.8cm long and 1.2cm wide; its coat is hard, bony-shiny and dark brown when broken reveals white colored cotyledons. Its leaves are elliptic to oblong (Emmanuel and Francis, 2010). The seed oil of ASA has rarely been reported for industrial purposes though it has been reported that its seed has an oil content between 7 – 25%. It is among the underutilized fruits in Nigeria.

The African Pear (AP) otherwise called African plum or Safou, locally called *ube* among the Igbo's in southern Eastern part of Nigeria belongs to the family of Burseraceae and botanically known as *Dacryodes eludis*. It is indigenous fruit tree grown in humid low lands and plateau regions of West central African and Gulf of Guinea country (Ogunsuyi 2015; Isaac, 2014). In south eastern Nigeria, the trees are grown around homesteads and flowering takes place from January to April with the major fruiting season between may and October. It is an annual fruit of about 3 cm in diameter and contains a leathery shelled stone surrounded by a pulpy pericarp of about 5 mm thick. It is this portion that is eaten either raw or cooked and the seeds discarded (Bull and George, 2015; Ogunsuyi, 2015).

Besides the pulp contains 48% oil and a plantation can produce 7-8 tonnes of oil per hectare (Awuno *et al.*, 2002; Shikha and Rita, 2012). The pericarp has the characteristics of butter and contains 48% oil in the pulp. Ogunsiyi *et al.*, 2015, obtained 59% oil from its seed which had an optimum biodiesel yield of 64% with the following amount of fatty acids (monounsaturated fatty acid – 76%, saturated fatty acid – 24%). Bull and George, 2015 in their study, obtained 80% biodiesel yield though the oil yield was not reported. However, no much work has been done in the use of African pear seed oil as a feedstock for biodiesel production.

Therefore, this study is undertaken to assess the viability of the seed oils from Sweet Almond, African Pear and African Star Apple in biodiesel production since their seeds are treated as wastes to enhance their economic potentials.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Materials

2. 1. 1. Reagents and Chemicals

Sodium hydroxide (99%, Sigma-Aldrich), potassium hydroxide (loba chemie, GmbH 85%), methanol ((Merck, Germany 99.5 % purity), carbon tetrachloride (chloroform), Wij's solution (iodine monochloride), potassium iodide solution, phenolphthalein (Merck Germany), powdered iodide (Fishon, England), hexane (99% purity, Merck Germany), sulphuric acid (98% min., Sg: 18300 BDH), hydrochloric acid, iodine, glacial acetic acid, iodine tetrachloride, starch indicator, potassium chloride, ethanol.

2. 1. 2. Apparatus and Analytical Equipment

Petri dishes, thermo regulator heater with Stirrer (Heizung chauffage, MGW-LAUDA, D6970, Lauda Konigshoffen, Germany). electric digital precision weighing balance (Ohaus, Adventurer, model – AR 3130), pH meter (Hanna pH meter, model: 02895, India), rotary evaporator oven (model BTOV 1423), veisfar muffle furnace (PEW, Path Electrical Mumbai, India), fenantic portable viscometer (model VL Brookfield Eng. Labline, USA), abbe refractometer (model: WAY-25, Search tech. Instruments), semi-automatic cleveland flash point tester, oxygen bomb calorimeter (model XRY-1A), top load balance (Binatone; model KS-7020), water still (2Lit/hr,model No: 7652, Medica Inst. Mgt Coy, India), concentric rings, thermostatic water bath (model no; 6801TI, 6 holes, medica Inst. Mgt Coy, India), pH meter, digital (Exstick, India), heating mantle (0-100 °C, Labline sunbine, India) and sohxlet extractor (BEHR, Labor- Technik Ez100).

2. 2. Test Materials/Sample Collection

2. 2. 1. Source of Seeds

The Fresh fruits were sourced from Onitsha City in Anambra State of Nigeria. Anambra State is located in the South Eastern part of Nigeria, linked with Delta State by the popular River Niger Bridge and shares boundaries with Enugu, Imo and Delta States. Geographically, Anambra State is located between latitude 5°37' 60N and longitude 7°10' 0E with equatorial type of climate.

2. 2. 2. Sample Preparation

The Fruits were washed properly and separated into seeds and pulp. The Clean seeds were sun-dried in the open for 7 days (for African Pear) while for Sweet Almond and African Star apple, the hulls containing the seeds were sun dried for 5 days to ensure free movement of the seed and indication for readiness for smooth seed separation. The seed were manually separated from hulls by cracking and the seeds collected were sun-dried in the open for 7 days.

Automatic Milling Machine was used to crush the seeds to obtain a size of 1.18 mm sieve size in order to weaken or rupture the cell walls to release the fat for extraction. The ground meal was further placed on solar dryer for a period of 3 days to remove residual moisture.

2. 3. Oil Extraction

2. 3. 1. Solvent Extraction

A known weight of the dried meal of seed was packed in a big fractionating column up to three quarter level and n-hexane was poured well above the level of the meal in the column. It

was closed with aluminum Foil and sealed with masking tape and then left for a period of 24 hrs. The mixture of oil and solvent was collected and filtered into a beaker. This was repeated to extract more oil from the meal. After which the oil was recovered using rotary evaporator to distill off the solvent. After distillation, the oil was left in the open to totally dry up the remaining solvent. The same process was applied for the other two fruit seed meals.

2. 3. 2. Oil Degumming

The oils were degummed to remove phosphophide, lysophasidid acids which are strong emulsifiers which lower the yields of neutral oil. This was done by mixing the crude oil with about 3% of warm water and the mixture was agitated mechanically for 30 minutes at 70 °C. This hydrates the phospholipids and gums thus making them insoluble in the oil. They were thereafter separated by settling.

2. 3. 3. Physico-Chemical Characterization of the Oil

The physic-chemical properties of the seed oils were determined in accordance with Association of Official Analytical Chemist (AOAC, 1990) method (the acid value by AOAC Ca5a-40, saponification value by AOAC 920:160; iodine value by AOAC 920:158 and peroxide value by AOAC 965.33) while the viscosity was determined by using Oswald viscometer apparatus, the density by using density bottle, moisture content by oven method, the ash content by heating to dryness in Veisfar Muffle furnace and the refractive index by using abbe refractometer (Model: WAY-25, Search tech. Instruments).

2. 4. Biodiesel Production

2. 4. 1. Preheating the oil

The oil was heated fairly at 80 °C for 30 minutes using Gallenkamp Magnetic Stirrer thermostat hot plate (Weiss Technik England) to reduce the viscosity of the oil.

2. 4. 2. Preparation of Sodium Methoxide

This was prepared by adding 2% weight of oil of NaOH to 175 ml of methanol and stirred at 300 rpm until it dissolved completely for about two minutes in the reaction vessel.

2. 4. 3. Transesterification Reaction

The Sweet Almond seed oil and Star Apple Seed Oil were subjected to direct base transesterification reaction while African Pear Seed Oil was subjected to two-step transesterification because of its high FFA. The two-step transesterification involves Acid transesterification followed by base transesterification.

2. 4. 3. 1. Acid transesterification

The transesterification was carried out using 50 ml of methanol and 0.2 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ mixed together inside a 250 ml conical Flask. The conical Flask was inserted into a water bath at 50 °C. The mixture was later added to 200 ml warmed (preheated) APSO inside a 500

ml conical flask and placed on magnetic stirrer with heater, continuously stirred for 1 hour 30 minutes for the acid transesterification to take place.

2. 4. 3. 2. Base Transesterification:

The SASO, ASASO and acid esterified APSO were subjected to base transesterification. The calculated amount of NaOH (Catalyst) and methanol was added for each reaction for the temperature and reaction time specified. The Base transesterification was carried out in a Soxhlet extractor fitted with thermo-regulator heater and stirrer. One hundred millilitre of oil was measured into the flask and was heated to the specified temperature. The Sodium methoxide was then poured into the flask containing oil and was immediately covered. The temperature was maintained for the specified time at constant agitation.

2. 4. 4. Separation of Biodiesel

After the base transesterification process the biodiesel was allowed to settle for 24 hours inside a separating funnel to allow clear separation of biodiesel from glycerin by gravity. The layer on the top is the biodiesel while the bottom layer is the glycerol. The Biodiesel separation was carried out by decanting as the glycerol was drained off while the biodiesel remained.

2. 4. 5. Biodiesel washing

Warm distilled water at 50 °C was added to the separated biodiesel and the mixture was shaken vigorously. The water was allowed to drain through the bottom of the separating funnel. This was carried out five times until a clear biodiesel was obtained.

2. 4. 6. Biodiesel Drying

Anhydrous CaCl₂ was added to the biodiesel and heated gently at 50 °C the anhydrous CaCl₂ was later separated from the biodiesel to obtain a clean dry biodiesel. The volume of the biodiesel obtained from each sample was determined while the percentage yield of biodiesel was calculated.

2. 4. 7. Physico chemical Characterization of the Biodiesel

The physico-chemical analyses of the seeds oil biodiesel were carried out using the Association of official Analytical Chemists method (AOAC, 1990). The analysis carried out includes: Pour point, cloud point, cloud point, flash point, refractive index, specific gravity, moisture content, viscosity, iodine value. The Cetane Index (CI) was determined using correlation given by Krisnamkura (1986) (Equation 10), Cetane Number (CN) was calculated by the equation developed by Patel (1999) (Equation 11), the FAME content in percentage was obtained by using correlation developed by Felizardo *et al.* (2006) (Equation 12), while the Higher Heating values were determined by using correlation applied by Sivaramkrishnan and Ravikumar, (2012) (Equations 13 to 16).

$$CI = 46.3 + (5458/SV) - 0.25IV \quad (10)$$

where: SV –Saponification Value, IV-Iodine Value

$$CN = CI - 2.6 \quad (11)$$

where: CI – Cetane Index

$$FAME \% = -45.055 \ln \mu + 162.85 \quad (12)$$

where: μ – kinematic viscosity

$$HHV = 0.0317V + 38.053 \text{ for vegetable oil} \quad (13)$$

$$= 0.4625V + 39.450 \text{ for biodiesel based on Viscosity} \quad (14)$$

$$= -0.0259\rho + 63.776 \text{ for biodiesel; based on density} \quad (15)$$

$$= 0.021FP + 32.12 \text{ for biodiesel based on flash point} \quad (16)$$

where: V-viscosity, ρ - density and FP – Flash point

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of SASO, APSO and ASASO

Sn	Parameters	Results		
			African Pear	African Star Apple
1.	Colour	Golden	Pale yellow	Dark red
2.	Specific gravity	0.8552	0.8885	0.8346
3.	Moisture content (%)	0.57	0.55	0.79
4.	Refractive Index	1.4472	1.4269	1.4515
5.	Saponification Value (mg KOH/g)	165.50	250.72	201.66
6.	Iodine Value (g/100g)	35.77	50.96	37.57
7.	Peroxide Value (milli eq. oxy/kg)	1.48	1.88	1.60
8.	Acid value (mg KOH/g)	2.805	6.57	2.88
9.	Free Fatty Acid as oleic (%)	1.402	3.28	1.44
10.	Ash Content (%)	1.02	1.50	1.22

11.	Viscosity (cp)	6.05	5.82	5.55
12.	Smoke point (°C)			
13.	Titre point (°C)			
14.	Flash point (°C)			
15.	Cloud point (°C)	-2		-3
16.	Yield (%)	60.15	55.70	13.36

Table 2. Result of the Seed Oil FAME Physico-chemical Characterization Compared with Standards

Parameter	Results			Standards		
	SASO FAME	APSO FAME	ASASO FAME	ASTM D 9751	ASTMD 6751	DIN 14214
Biodiesel Yield (%)	94.36	93.025	86.49	-	-	-
Specific gravity	0.8491	0.5517	8195	850	880	860-900
Moisture content (%)	0.02	0.031	0.026	-	-	-
Refractive Index	1.4402	1.4269	1.4438	-	-	-
Acid value (mgKOH/g)	0.46	0.92	0.32	0.062	0.50	0.50
Free fatty acid (%)	0.23	0.46	0.16	0.31	0.25	0.25
Iodine value (mgKOH/g)	28.02	45.06	32.86	42-46	-	120max.
Saponification value (mgKOH/g)	161.05	242.51	189.03	-	-	-
Ash Content (%)	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.01	0.02	0.02
Viscosity (cp)	2.84	2.31	2.19	2.6	1.9-6.0	3.5-5.0
Smoke point			25	-	-	-
Fire point			36	-	-	-
Flash point			126	60-80	100-170	120
Cloud point	-2		-3	-20	-3 to 12	-

Pour point	-6		-8	-35	-15 to -16	-
Calorific Value (KJ/Kg)	31,178.39	34,421.50	32,838.38	42-46	-	35
Conductivity (Us/CM)	0.40	0.86	0.52	-	-	-
Cetane Index	73.0	57.80	67.16	-	-	-
Cetane Number	70.40	55.20	64.57	40-55	47min	51min
Higher Heating Value (HHV) ^a (MJ/kg)	34.72	34.50	34.52	-	-	-
Higher Heating Value (HHV) ^b (MJ/kg)	40.76	40.52	40.46	-	-	-
Higher Heating Value (HHV) ^c (MJ/kg)	63.75	63.75	63.75	-	-	-

^a - Based on Flash point, ^b - based on Viscosity, ^c - based on density, min-minimum, max- maximum

3. 1. Oil and Biodiesel Yield

The oil content is a key factor influencing the choice of plant seeds as potential feedstock for biodiesel and other industrial products. The percentage oil yield from SA and AP (60.15% and 55.70% respectively) appear more encouraging for biofuel purposes than ASA seed oil yield of 13.36% which is quite low when compared with most oil feedstocks (peanut – 50%, sesame seed – 5-% olive seed – 40%, castor seed - 50%, sunflower seed – 35%) as reported by Ofoefule *et al.*, (2013). This indicates that the ASA seed may not be a good seed of abundant oil for biodiesel production but genetically modified breeds may be developed which could produce seeds with higher oil yields.

3. 2. Oil Colour

The golden and pale yellow colours of SASO and APSO are of high aesthetic qualities while that of ASASO is dark red. The results are the same with the colours obtained by earlier researchers while ASASO compares well in colour with *Luffa Cylindrica* and *Cucumis melo* (Ibeto *et al.*, 2012).

3. 3. The moisture contents

The high moisture content of vegetable oil is an indication of poor processing practice; it promotes oil oxidation rancidity and equally affects the biodiesel yield negatively.

The results obtained for SASO – 0.59%, APSO – 0.55% and ASASO – 0.79%, are all quite low compared with 5.32% obtained by Ofoefule *et al.*, 2013 for tiger nut seed oil and 5.006% by Isreal, 2008 for Almond seed oil. Lotero *et al.*, 2005 has advised for moisture content of vegetable oils to be lower than 0.5% in order to obtain up to 90% yield of biodiesel. The values obtained in this study had no negative effect on the quality of methyl esters produced from any of the seed oils.

3. 4. The Saponification Values

The saponification value serves as important parameters in determining the suitability of the oil for soap making and inversely proportional to the molecular weight of the oil (Audu *et al.*, 2012). Therefore it can be deduced that the value of 165.50 mg KOH/g, 250.72 mg KOH/g and 201.68 mg KOH/g for SASO, APSO and ASASO could indicate that SASO would be more useful in biodiesel production, followed by ASASO and APSO because APSO would have more tendency of soap formation than ASASO while ASASO would produce more soap during transesterification than SASO. The values obtained are in appreciable consistency with the literature values especially from ASASO: Audu *et al.*, 2013 obtained 193.7 mg KOH/g, Musal *et al.*, 2015 obtained 228 mg KOH/g though Agbede *et al.*, 2012 obtained 327 mg KOH/g while Ochigbo and Paiko 2011 got 246.84 mg KOH/g. The value 165.50 mg KOH/g obtained for SASO indicates that it is made up of low concentration of triglycerides (Adepoju and Olawale, 2014) or high proportion of fatty acids of low molecular weight (Musa *et al.*, 2015). The value is more than twice the value 65.92 mg KOH/g reported for *Luffa Cylindrica* by Ibeto *et al.*, 2012 and higher than 161.1 mg KOH/g reported by Ofoefule *et al.*, 2012 for tiger nut. The Saponification value of 250.72 mg KOH/g was obtained from APSO and it appeared highest among the three seed oil samples used. The high result is in agreement with the values of 250 mg KOH/g and 253 mg KOH/g reported for edible oil like palm kernel oil and coconut oil respectively as reported by Musa *et al.*, 2015 but far higher than the value of 171.10 mg KOH/g reported by Ogunsuyi, 2015 from African Pear. The saponification value of the methyl esters quite decreased when compared with the values obtained from the seed oils and follows the trends observed in tiger nut oil (Ofoefule *et al.*, 2013) and corn oil (De lima *et al.*, 2013). The value obtained from APSOME was the lowest (161.05 mg KOH/g).

3. 5. The iodine Values

The iodine values obtained are 50.96 mg KOH/g, 37.57 mg KOH/g and 35.77 mg KOH/g for APSO, ASASO and SASO respectively. Iodine value is the measure of degree of unsaturation of an oil (Nzikou *et al.*, 2009). Iodine value is classified thus, greater than 130 (drying) between 150 and 130 (semi-drying) and less than 115 non-drying. Therefore, all the three oil samples are all non-drying oil samples. The iodine value according to EN 14214 (European committee for standardization) should be less than 120 g I₂/100 g sample for the seed oil to be suitable as feedstock for biodiesel production while oils having high unsaturation of fatty acids, when heated are prone to polymerization of the glycerides, causing formation of deposits and thereby compromising oxidative stability, (Mittelbach, 1996). Therefore, the values obtained for the three seed oils, do not suggest high unsaturation. Also Giwa and Ogunbona, 2014 obtained 92.3 mg KOH/g for SASO, Audu *et al.*, 2013 obtained 33.18 mg KOH/g and 83.56 mg KOH/g for ASASO and *Luffa Cylindrica*, Musa *et al.*, 2015 obtained 30.0 mg KOH/g for ASASO. Literature value for APSO is rare. The iodine value is an index of the number of double bonds within a mixture of fatty acid contained in biodiesel. Therefore, it is a measure of the total unsaturation of a fatty material. The iodine value of SASOME, APSOME and ASASOME are 28.02 mg KOH/g, 45.06 mg KOH/g and 32.86 mg KOH/g respectively showing slight decrease in the values obtained from the parent seed oils. The above values satisfy the specification of 120 g I/100 g (maximum) recommended by

EN14214 standards. Iodine value of APSOME is highest and this indicates that it may possess the highest fatty acid among the three methyl esters produced. The values are lower than 98.38 for tiger nut biodiesel (Ofoefule *et al.*, 2013) which indicates higher saturation in the results obtained in this research.

3. 6. Peroxide Values